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Deliverable 2.8

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How to Cite

Burrows, M.T., Assis, J., Principe, S.C. 2024. Climate velocity map for European seas under recent conditions. Nord University, *MPA Europe Project Report Deliverable 2.8*, 15 pp.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14659560>

Version: V1.0

Data of release: 15th of January 2025

Instrument call: HORIZON-CL6-2021-BIODIV-01-12

Start of the project: 1st January 2023

Duration of the project: 40 months

Co-funded by
the European Union

UK Research
and Innovation

MPA Europe is co-funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe programme (Grant Agreement: 101059988). UK participants in Horizon Europe Project *MPA Europe* are supported by UKRI grant numbers 10067934 JNCC and 10069750 SAMS.

Views and opinions expressed are those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect that of the European Union or UK Research and Innovation. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

The report represents the most up to date status of the information. Any potential upcoming information may be considered for incorporation in future deliverables to improve the scientific knowledge.

The MPA Europe project

MPA Europe is a project co-funded by the European Union (EU) that will map a network of locations representative of biodiversity in European seas (Atlantic Exclusive Economic Zones of the EU and its neighbours, and all the Mediterranean, Baltic, and Black seas) (Figure A).

Figure A. MPA Europe study area.

This network will indicate where to prioritise placement of Marine Protected Areas (MPA) for biodiversity protection and how Maritime Spatial Planning (MSP) can maximise blue carbon benefits. By using a holistic set of biodiversity measures, from species to ecosystems (including habitats), and environmental data including carbon storage, water currents, and climate change velocity models, it will be possible to quantify and map both the present and future connectivity within the proposed MPA network. The multiple scenarios provided will support wider and improved MSP by policy makers, industry, and non-governmental organizations (NGOs). The major scientific areas of the project and its outcomes are summarized in the infographic presented in Figure Figure B.

Figure B. MPA Europe project scientific areas

The inter-disciplinary approach of MPA Europe is supported by a diversity of partners. These include Nord University (Norway), the Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission of UNESCO (Belgium), Aarhus University (Denmark), Climazul (Greece), the Centre of Marine Sciences (Portugal), Science Crunchers (Portugal), the Joint Nature Conservation Committee (England, UK), the Scottish Association for Marine Science (Scotland, UK), the Ocean University of China (China), and the University of the Ryukyus (Japan). The partners include experts in marine biology, taxonomy, ecology, oceanography, biogeochemistry, and biogeography, MPA network design, benthic habitat mapping, carbon dynamics, species distribution, climate modelling, and MSP compose the MPA Europe team.

Deliverable 2.8 overview

This report outlines the creation of the climate velocity map for the MPA Europe study area under current conditions. The environmental layers established in Deliverable 2.1 (Assis et al. 2023) form the basis for calculating climate velocity, which represents the rate and direction of spatial climate shifts over time (Burrows et al. 2011; Devictor et al. 2008). This description and map will act as a reference for the prioritization analysis focused on designing a Marine Protected Area (MPA) network to promote biodiversity conservation and blue carbon. Through this process, the most effective MPA networks covering 10% and 30% of European seas will be identified to maximize benefits for biodiversity, blue carbon, and their combined advantages.

Background

The velocity of climate change expresses the rate and direction of spatial shifts in climate over time (Burrows et al. 2011; Devictor et al. 2008) and has proved to be a useful and universal predictor of global shifts in species distributions in the ocean (Pinsky et al. 2013; Poloczanska et al. 2013, 2014). Climate velocity can also show how global patterns of biodiversity might change under climate warming (García Molinos et al. 2016) and where geographical barriers might prevent or hinder the poleward spread of species through areas of newly suitable climate (Burrows et al. 2014). The product has been widely used in global assessments of impacts of climate change on natural ecological systems (IPCC, Poloczanska et al. 2014) and on society and people (IPCC/IPBES, Pörtner et al. 2023). Climate trajectories derived from velocity fields have useful implications for changes in biodiversity with climate, especially when their collective spatial behaviour is divided into classes, such as climate ‘sources’ and ‘sinks’ and areas of slow and rapid shifts. A summary of the implications of these classes is given in Table 1.

As part of Work package 2 (Ecosystem and connectivity modelling) of MPA Europe, we aim to use maps of current and future climate velocity across European seas to assess how well a proposed MPA network will facilitate species range shifts responding to climate change, through the inclusion of present as well as future biodiversity. This deliverable represents the first step in this process. Velocity of climate change maps are planned for Deliverable 2.9 using projected climate change scenarios (Shared Socioeconomic Pathways, SSP) spanning from high mitigation (SSP119 matching the Paris Agreement) to business-as-usual scenarios (SSP585, ‘Fossil-fueled Development’).

Methods

We used sea surface temperature data from Bio-Oracle (Assis et al. 2018, Assis et al. 2023) (<https://www.bio-oracle.org/>) for present day and projected future conditions of European seas. Climate velocities were calculated using the methods of Burrows et al. (2011, 2014) incorporated into an R library (García Molinos et al. 2019), modified to produce maps of the velocity (speed and direction) of climate change. The model domain was chosen to include areas south of Europe where future conditions for European seas currently exist.

Two sets of climate velocity maps were produced. For climate velocity representing recent conditions (this deliverable), the sea surface temperature climatology as average temperatures for 1940-1960 was compared to that for 2000-2020. Current conditions extend beyond the end of the second of these time periods, so a second set of maps were produced using a comparison of temperatures between 2000-2020 and projected 2040-2060 sea surface temperatures under SSP370 from 2000-2020 to 2040-2050. (Meinshausen et al. 2020; Riahi et al. 2017). SSP370 (‘Regional rivalry’) represents expected warming under a radiative forcing of 7 w/m², leading to a global warming of about 4 to 5 °C above the preindustrial levels by 2100 in a world where nationalism and regional conflicts overshadow global issues (‘The SSP Scenarios’ 2025).

For velocity calculations, trends in temperature (°C/yr) for each 0.05-degree latitude-longitude grid cell were obtained using the differences between the two periods, divided by the duration between the two period mid points, being 60 years (1950 to 2010). Velocity of climate was thus determined as the ratio of the trend in temperature to the local spatial gradient of average temperatures across the two periods. Direction of climate velocity was derived from the direction of the local spatial gradients in temperature around each grid cell. The sign of climate velocity reflects the sign of the trend in temperature: positive thermal velocities occur in areas of warming and negative thermal velocities in areas of cooling. Positive velocities are directed towards locally cooler areas while negative velocities are directed towards locally warmer areas.

Climate trajectories (Burrows et al. 2014), the paths that points on isotherms are expected to follow over time were calculated using temperatures and velocities downscaled to 0.1-degree resolution from the original 0.05-degree resolution. Since trajectories follow local velocities, in areas of warming, positive velocities mean that trajectories show isotherm shifts towards locally cooler places, while in areas of cooling, trajectories show isotherm shifts towards locally warmer areas.

Trajectory classes across the velocity maps were evaluated by obtaining counts of trajectories that started, ended and crossed 0.2-degree grid cells. For comparison with the earlier study, done globally at a 1-degree resolution, trajectory counts were aggregated in a 1-degree neighbourhood around each grid cell. The aggregated counts were then used to calculate the proportions of cells that started, ended and flowed through the cells in the neighbourhood, and used to classify cells following the process shown in Figure 1.

The scripts used for the analyses described in this report, along with the adapted version of the VoCC package (García Molinos et al., 2019), are available in the GitHub repository: https://github.com/iobis/mpaeu_climatevelocity.

Results

Maps of the velocity of climate change follow the patterns of spatial gradients and temporal trends in temperature (Figure 2). Velocity is positive where the temporal trend in temperature is warming (Figure 2 bottom right) and negative when cooling. Higher velocities emerge where spatial gradients in temperature are shallow (Figure 2 bottom middle: green areas) and lower where gradients are steep. For the projected current trends in temperature across European seas under SSP370 (Figure 2 top), highest velocities are projected for the southern Atlantic region, the Mediterranean, the North Sea and the Baltic. Lowest values for the magnitude of velocity, including negative values, are seen in an area of cooling south of Iceland and west of Scotland and Ireland, and locally spatial gradients in temperature are steep, such as along coastlines with strong upwelling in Portugal and Morocco.

Broad similarities are apparent between velocity maps for current (Figure 3, 2010-2050) and recent (Figure 4, 1950-2010) periods. Both show a large area of low of cooling west of Ireland and high velocity areas in the North Sea, the Mediterranean and areas off Scandinavia. While the sign (negative or positive) of velocity is driven by the sign of temperature trends, the magnitude of velocity is strongly influenced by the spatial gradients in temperature. Since spatial gradients are driven by oceanographic features that are expected to persist over time, such correspondence in patterns of directions of velocity particularly is expected.

Some evidence of artefacts in patterns of velocity are suggested for the maps of climate velocity for recent change (Figure 4). There are many trajectories apparently ‘channelled’ along lines of longitude. This may be an effect of the methods used to produce the original SST data, perhaps associated with upscaling from lower resolution source data to 0.05-degree resolution.

The operation of climate trajectories can be better seen on regional maps (Figure 5). Trajectory lines are most elongated in areas of high velocity (Figure 5 top left), and in areas of warming are directed from locally warm areas towards locally cool areas (i.e. positive velocities), as shown by local spatial anomalies in temperature (Figure 5 top right, bottom right). Spatial anomalies were calculated as the temperatures in each grid cell minus the local average temperature over the surrounding 1-degree latitude-longitude area. Locally cool areas appear along Atlantic coastlines of Portugal and North Africa, all along the west coast of Norway (Figure 5 bottom right). Coastal areas are locally warmer

along the north facing coasts of North Africa, Turkey and the North Sea coasts of France and Germany. Trajectories head away from the coasts where such coasts are locally warmer.

Maps of the classification of trajectory behaviour for current (Figure 6, 2010-2050) and recent (Figure 7, 1950-2010) periods also show similarities. Unlike the earlier studies, climate ‘sources’, areas where no direct connections exist to warmer places to allow species distributions to expand, are found offshore in the centres of regional seas as in the Mediterranean and North Sea or offshore between locally cool coastal areas and even cooler ocean regions, as off the coast of northern Spain.

Discussion

Maps produced in this project represent an advance on earlier versions of climate velocity maps for European seas (Burrows et al. 2011, 2014) being at much higher resolution: 0.1-degree latitude and longitude resolution for trajectories and 0.2-degree resolution for climate trajectory classes. However, the higher resolution does change spatial patterns of velocity at smaller scales. Climate velocity has been shown in other studies to be very scale-dependent, particularly on land, with local variations in temperature driving speed and direction of velocity towards local features, such as mountains, at high resolutions and geographical-scale variations in temperature driving directions generally polewards at larger scales (Dobrowski et al. 2013). This effect is evident in the velocity maps for the recent (1950-2010, Figure 4) and current periods (2010-2050, Figure 3). Earlier analysis using 1-degree data (HadISST v1.1, (Burrows et al. 2011) showed similar rapid velocities in the North Sea (>20 km/yr), for example, that were generally poleward (Figure 3a of Burrows et al. (Burrows et al. 2014)). For example, velocity maps at 0.1-degree (Figure 3, Figure 4) show broadly similar large scale geographical patterns in speed of climate shifts, with rapid velocities in the North Sea, but very different directions, particularly in coastal areas where climate velocity is mostly oriented towards locally cooler coastlines. Such local spatial variation is averaged out at larger spatial scales. The different implications for shifts in species distributions of these differences in outcomes at different spatial resolution will require careful consideration for the implications for biodiversity (Table 1). They may indicate locations where there will be little or no temperature change and which may be considered thermal refugia, and areas with relatively high warming which may see changes in species’ abundance due to climate warming.

A full discussion and matching of patterns seen here and their associations with patterns of biodiversity, blue carbon reserves and the European MPA network will appear in later deliverables for MPA Europe.

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Table 1. Summary of trajectory classes, with implications for species range shifts if species distributions track shifting climatic niches. Descriptions of climate sources and sinks and their effects are for warming regions (from Burrows et al. 2014).

Trajectory Class	Climate connectivity	Effects on population distributions	Effects on species richness
Climate Sources	Disconnected from warmer locales	High emigration. No climate immigration.	Species richness declines as climate emigrants not replaced.
Climate Sinks	Disconnected from cooler locales	Species have no adjacent cooler place to relocate. No climate emigration. High climate immigration.	Local extirpation possible, but lost species replaced. Richness stable .
Climate Corridors	Pathways of strong or intense isotherm movement	Species arriving from geographically distant locations. High emigration and immigration.	Richness stable or increased.
Convergence and Divergence	Areas where isotherms gather or disperse	Moderate emigration and immigration	Richness change depends on balance of emigrants and immigrants.
Low-velocity areas	Climate change does not propagate rapidly across the surface	Little, or slow change in species composition and distribution.	Little change.

Figure 1. Climate velocity trajectory rules for assignment of areas of change into biodiversity-relevant classes, modified from Figure 1 of Burrows et al. (2014).

Figure 2. Components of the velocity of climate change for Europe, including the: (a) direction of spatial gradients in temperature (North, yellow; West, green; South, blue; East, red) (bottom left); (b) magnitude of spatial gradients in temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{km}$; green shallow, purple steep) (bottom middle); (c) projected rate of change in temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{year}$; blue cooling, read warming) (bottom right). Temperatures were based on projections from Shared Socioeconomic Pathway SSP370 from 2000-2020 to 2040-2050.

Figure 3. Velocity of climate change for sea surface temperature in European seas, based on projected climate change under Shared Socioeconomic Pathway SSP370 from 2000-2020 to 2040-2050. Lines show climate velocity trajectories: the shifts in points of given temperature over the 40-year period from their start at the centre of grid cells in 2010 to their end in 2050, moving annually at the pace of local velocity. The magnitude of climate velocity is shown by the underlying colour: red in areas of high velocity, yellow in low or zero velocity and green to blue in areas of negative velocity where temperatures are projected to cool.

Figure 4. The velocity of climate change for sea surface temperature in European seas, based on climate change from 1940-1960 to 2000-2020. The black lines show climate velocity trajectories, the shifts in temperature over the 60-year period from a start at the centre of each grid cell in 1950 to their end in 2010 when following local velocity of climate change. Colours show the magnitude of climate velocity as in Figure 2 and Figure 3 (see box legend).

Figure 5. Close up views (1:5000000) of: climate velocity and associated climate trajectories (top left); climate trajectories with local temperature anomalies relative to larger-scale 1-degree latitude-longitude area averages (top right); and the assignment of climate trajectories into biodiversity-relevant classes (bottom left). Temperatures were based on projections from SSP370 from 2000-2020 to 2040-2050. Climate velocity (top left) is highest in areas of rapid temperature increase and shallow spatial gradients in temperature and is directed away from areas of locally warm water (top right in red) towards locally cooler areas (blue). Trajectory behaviour was assigned to classes (Figure 1) based on the magnitude of local velocity and the proportional frequency of trajectory starts, endings and transits across grid cells. Coastal Boundary Sinks are not shown. Local SST spatial anomalies at a European scale show areas of relative cold and warmth (bottom right).

Figure 6. Climate velocity trajectory classes for climate velocity of sea surface temperature in European seas, based on projected climate change under Shared Socioeconomic Pathway SSP370 from 2000-2020 to 2040-2050. Climate trajectories are shown as in Figure 3.

Figure 7. Climate velocity trajectory classes for climate velocity of sea surface temperature in European seas based on climate change from 1940-1960 to 2000-2020. Climate trajectories are shown as in Figure 3.

